

SHORT NOTES

Synthesis of 2-Halo-5-thienylsulphonylhydrazones and 1-(2-Halo-5-thienyl)sulphonyl-4-substituted Thiosemicarbazides

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In continuation of the earlier work¹ from this laboratory, several 2-halo-5-thienylsulphonylhydrazine hydrochlorides, 2-halo-5-thienylsulphonylhydrazones, and 1-(2-halo-5-thienyl)sulphonyl-4-substituted thiosemicarbazides have been synthesised.

2-Chlorothiophene was prepared according to Campaigne and Lesuer² and 2-bromothiophene according to Blick and Burkhalter³. 2-Halo-5-thienylsulphonylhydrazine hydrochlorides, needed as starting materials for this work, were prepared from the related sulphonyl chlorides⁴. The corresponding hydrazones (I) and thiosemicarbazides (II) were synthesised by condensing these sulphonylhydrazine hydrochlorides with various aldehydes and isothiocyanates respectively (Tables I and II).

2-Halo-5-thienylsulphonylhydrazine hydrochlorides were prepared from the corresponding sulphonyl chlorides by the method described earlier¹.

2-Chloro-5-thienylsulphonylhydrazine hydrochloride was obtained as colorless plates, m.p. 133° (ethanol), yield 51%. (Found: N, 11.1; S, 25.6. C₄H₆O₂N₂Cl₂S₂ requires N, 11.3; S, 25.7%).

2-Bromo-5-thienylsulphonylhydrazine hydrochloride was obtained as colorless plates, m.p. 131° (ethanol), yield 52%. (Found: N, 9.4; S, 21.5. C₄H₆O₂N₂BrClS₂ requires N, 9.5; S, 21.8%).

1. Munshi *et al.*, *Indian Chem. J.*, 1963, 1, 311, 318.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 415.

3. *Ibid.*, 1942, 64, 477.

4. Steinkopf *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1937, 532, 250; 1934, 512, 136.

TABLE I
 2-Halo-5-(thienyl)sulphonylhydrazones.

R.	Formula.	M.P.	% Sulphur.		% Nitrogen.		M.P.	B. X = Br.		Found.	Reqd.
			A. X=Cl.	Found.	Found.	Reqd.		Found.	Reqd.		
C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	84°	21.3	21.3	9.0	9.3	89°	18.5	18.6	8.0	7.1
o-HOC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	211-12°	20.0	20.2	8.6	8.8	215-16°	17.6	17.7	7.8	7.8
p-HOC ₆ H ₄	"	86°	20.1	20.2	8.7	8.8	88°	17.5	17.7	7.7	7.8
o-C ₁₀ H ₇	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	147°	18.0	18.3	8.0	8.0	156-57°	16.0	16.2	7.0	7.1
p-(CH ₂) ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	79-80°	18.5	18.0	12.0	12.2	93°	16.4	16.5	10.6	10.8
p-(OH)(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄ XS ₂	154°	18.5	18.5	7.0	8.1	169-71°	16.4	16.4	7.0	7.2
2,4-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₁ H ₇ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	211-12°	17.2	17.3	7.5	7.6	208-10°	15.3	15.5	6.7	6.8
p-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	90-91°	20.2	20.4	8.9	8.9	80-81°	17.7	17.8	7.5	7.8
o-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	81-83°	20.3	20.4	8.7	8.9	86-87°	17.7	17.8	7.6	7.8
p-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	156°	19.4	19.4	8.3	8.6	169-70°	17.0	17.1	7.5	7.5
3-(CH ₃) ₂ N ₂ C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₂ H ₉ N ₅ O ₂ XS ₂	198-99°	18.3	18.6	8.0	8.1	204-205°	16.4	16.5	7.1	7.2
C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH.	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	180-91°	19.5	19.6	8.5	8.6	164-67°	17.0	17.2	7.2	7.6

 TABLE II
 1-(2'-halo-5'-(thienyl)sulphonyl-4-substituted thiazemitarbazides.

R.	Formula.	M.P.	% Sulphur.		% Nitrogen.		M.P.	B. X = Br.		Found.	Reqd.
			A. X=Cl.	Found.	Found.	Reqd.		Found.	Reqd.		
C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	201°	27.3	27.6	12.0	12.1	189°	24.3	24.5	10.5	10.7
C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	208-204°	26.3	26.6	11.4	11.6	148-49°	23.3	23.6	10.2	10.4
p-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	"	213-14°	26.4	26.6	11.4	11.6	214°	23.4	23.6	10.2	10.4
o-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	"	168°	26.6	26.6	11.6	11.6	176-77°	23.3	23.6	10.3	10.4
p-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	216-17°	25.2	25.4	10.9	11.1	224°	22.6	22.8	9.8	10.0
p-ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₇ ClN ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	220-22°	25.0	25.1	10.8	11.0	216°	22.2	22.5	9.6	9.8
p-BrC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₁ H ₇ BrN ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	224-25°	22.3	22.5	6.7	6.9	218-19°	20.1	20.4	8.6	8.9
O ₂ H ₂	C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ O ₂ XS ₂	67-80°	29.0	29.3	12.6	12.8	115-16°	26.6	26.6	11.1	11.3

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